

WAYS TO IMPROVE THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISM FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE SECTOR IN RURAL AREAS

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada qishloq joylarda xizmatlar sohasini rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish yo'llari keltirilgan.

Tauanch so'zlar. xizmatlar sohasi, qishloq joylar, bandlik, turmush darajasi, raqamli texnologiyalar, innovatsion faoliyat.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлены пути совершенствования организационно-экономического механизма развития сферы услуг в сельской местности.

Ключевые слова: сфера услуг, сельская местность, занятость, уровень жизни, цифровые технологии, инновационная деятельность.

Annotation. This article presents ways to improve the organizational and economic mechanism for the development of the service sector in rural areas..

Key words: service sector, rural areas, employment, living standards, digital technologies, innovative activities.

In the current conditions of globalization, the development of all sectors of the economy, in particular, the service sector in rural areas, is becoming increasingly important. The service sector plays a significant role in improving the living standards of the rural population, increasing employment, improving social infrastructure, and eliminating regional imbalances. However, there are a number of organizational, financial, and institutional problems in the development of this area [1].

In rural areas, the service sector is not sufficiently developed. This leads to incomplete satisfaction of the population's needs, high unemployment rates, limited local budgets, and increased external migration. Therefore, the revision and improvement of the organizational and economic mechanisms for the development of the service sector is relevant [2].

At the present stage of human civilization, the service sector is becoming an integral part of the economy, and its increasing role in shaping the standard and quality of life of the population increases the need for its rapid development. It is this necessity that determines the development of the service sector as a priority task and requires the development and systematic implementation of measures

and ways to implement it. In our opinion, it is necessary to substantiate that the rapid development of the service sector and strengthening its position in the socio-economic life of the country is not just a simple measure, but an important direction of strategic development for the long term. Solving this important task is primarily related to revealing the socio-economic significance of the service sector in the formation of a post-industrial society [3].

The service sector is an important link in the real sector of the economy, encompassing commerce, information, education, medicine, transport, finance, tourism, and many other areas. The development of this sector contributes to: providing new types of services for rural residents, creating new jobs, increasing household incomes, and developing entrepreneurship in rural areas [4].

Obstacles to the development of the service sector:

- Shortage of material and technical base;
- Limited access to financial resources;
- Low knowledge of marketing and management;
- underdevelopment of public-private partnership (PPP) mechanisms;
- Low demand for services among the population (if there is a lack of advertising, information).

Proposals for improving the organizational and economic mechanism:

• Integration of the service sector into the regional development strategy. Development of separate strategies for the development of the service sector at the district or regional level.

• Creation of tax and financial benefits. Improvement of tax holidays, subsidies, and loan guarantees for entrepreneurs investing in the service sector.

• Creation and modernization of service infrastructure. In particular, the development of infrastructure for digital services (trade via the Internet, distance learning, telemedicine).

• Creation of a personnel training and retraining system. Creation of vocational training centers in rural areas and the introduction of training courses in the service sector.

• Expansion of public-private partnership mechanisms. Organization in the regions of car services, pharmacies, notaries, financial centers, and information services based on PPPs.

• Development of local brands and tourism. Expansion of the service sector through local handicrafts, national cuisine, and agritourism services.

• Implementation of foreign experience. For example, the experience of India and Turkey - service models based on small businesses.

The development of the service sector in rural areas is an important factor in ensuring economic growth, improving the well-being of the population, and ensuring regional stability. To solve the problems in this area, not only financial assistance is needed, but also systemic, targeted, and harmonized organizational and economic mechanisms. These mechanisms should be based on local resources, the needs of the population, and new technologies.

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